

Scientific Report

Flood in North Bank of Brahmaputra River and its Effects on Human Life and Bioresources in the Butikur area of Dhemaji District, Assam

Hemchandra Kalita^{1*} and Sunil Konch²

¹Bordoloni Higher Secondary School, Dhemaji, Assam, INDIA

²Batgharia Higher Secondary School, Dhemaji, Assam, INDIA

*Corresponding author: kalitahemchandra9@gmail.com

Received: October 10, 2023; revised: December 20, 2023; accepted: December 25, 2023

Published Online: December, 2023

Introduction

The north east India surrounded by the hills and mountains of Mount Himalaya is enriched by the bioresources as well as famous for mighty Brahmaputra River. The Brahmaputra river flowing from eastern tip of state Assam to the Western and finally to the Bay of Bengal has bifurcate the state into north and south bank. The indigenous native people of the state are living in the fertile Brahmaputra basin since yore. The whole Brahmaputra basis is inundated by flood water from east to west and from north to south during monsoon every year. Dhemaji district at the eastern part of Assam and north bank of Brahmaputra River covers an area of 3237 Sq. Km (Fig. 1) with a population of approximately 7,91,523(Census, 2011). The district is interwoven by a number tributaries of Brahmaputra River namely ,Simen ,Gainadi, Karha , Jiadhhal and Subansiri River. People of the district experience flood every year during monsoon that have been described in various literature (Bhoben Pegu, 1990; Umesh Chetia, 1994, 2009). In the Dhemaji district , the Butikur area located about 10 Km south side from Dhemaji town is extremely affected by flood water of Karha and Jiadhhal rivers. The persistent floods, occurring from May to September, consistently devastate crops, properties, and livelihoods of both humans and animals in the area. On this background the present study has been carried out in five villages namely: 1. Hatipara, 2., Butikur, 3. Kacharipothar, 4. Bordheker and

(A)

(B)

Fig. 1 . (A and B) Map of Dhemaji district, Assam (India).

5. Hiloipara of Butikur area (Fig. 2) with an objective of assessing poverty, literacy as well the quality of life of rural communities. First hand information have been collected in

Conclusion

Improving the situation in the Butikur area necessitates a comprehensive approach involving both community-driven initiatives and strong governmental support.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the villagers of Batikur area of Dhemaji district for their support and cooperation in data collection as well as giving necessary information.

References

- Bhoben Pegu (1990).** Jiadhok Bhetibo Kone (Who will stop Jiadhok River). Janata Printers. Dhemaji, Assam
- Umesh Chetia (2009).** Dhemajir Buranji (History of Dhemaji). Kiran Prakashan, Dhemaji, Assam
- Umesh Chetia (1994).** Dhemajir Sokulo (The Weeping Dhemaji). News paper article. Dhemaji, Assam